

Neutral reduction with titanium powder.—Neutral reductions with titanium powder were not very satisfactory, since in each case the yield was very low. The reductions were carried on according to the method of Lal and Dutt.

Picramic acid from picric acid.—The yield was only 0.5 g. from 2 g. of picric acid. *Benzhydrol from benzophenone.*—The yield was 0.66 g. from 2 g. of benzophenone. *o-Aminophenol from o-nitrophenol.*—Yield was 0.2 g. from 2 g. *Aniline from nitrobenzene.*—The yield was 3 g. from 10 g.

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Parachor and Chemical Constitution. Part IV. The Structure of Aliphatic Diazo-compounds.

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In spite of much work done by various investigators for more than fifty years, the constitution of the aliphatic diazo-compounds has not yet been definitely settled. Curtius (*Ber.*, 1883, **16**, 2230), who discovered these compounds, proposed the structure (I) while Angeli (*Atti. R. Accad. Lincei*, 1907, *ii* **16**, 790) first pointed out that the reactions of these compounds are best represented by the structure (II)

(I)

(II)

which was further advocated by Thiele (*Ber.*, 1911, **44**, 2552). Both the ring structure of Curtius and the open-chain structure of Angeli-Thiele, have been supported by different investigators from time to time, and it is not possible from a perusal of the literature on the subject to arrive at a definite conclusion. The reactions which these compounds undergo can be explained equally well by means of either the Curtius or the Angeli-Thiele formula. These facts led the present author to attempt at a solution of the problem by determining the parachor of these compounds, the difference in the parachor between the two forms being sufficiently large for a definite decision to be possible by each measurement. It was noted by many investiga-

tors that these compounds gradually change their colour on heating, the original colour reappearing on cooling. All these facts point out that these substances are probably equilibrium mixtures of the two forms, the proportion of the either form present may possibly depend on temperature. The present work was undertaken to find out the parachor of these compounds at different temperatures in order to determine their constitution and to find out whether it depends on the temperature.

In the present paper data are given for four diazo-acetic esters at five different temperatures for each. The surface tension was determined by the method of maximum bubble pressure as in the earlier works.

The compounds were prepared by the method of Curtius (*loc. cit.*). The purification of the impure diazo compounds offered considerable difficulty. Steam distillation (except in the case of the methyl ester) in small quantities, as recommended by Curtius, was found to be the best method of purification, although a large part of the diazo compound is lost thereby. The compounds were finally purified by distillation under low pressure. As the action of light changes these substances to a greater or less extent, all the operations are to be performed in very dim light. These compounds are also decomposed on keeping, hence observations should be made only with freshly prepared samples. Even on keeping for a few hours the surface tension was found to change appreciably.

The observed values of the parachor are given in the fourth column of the following tables, the calculated parachors for the different forms are also given therein.

TABLE I.

<i>Diazo-acetic methyl ester.</i>				<i>Diazo-acetic ethyl ester.</i>			
Temp.	Density.	Surface tension.	$P_{obs.}$	Temp.	Density.	Surface tension	$P_{obs.}$
0°	1.191	37.51	207.8	0°	1.114	35.00	249.0
20°	1.173	35.36	207.9	20°	1.080	32.05	251.2
30°	1.118	34.86	211.6	30°·5	1.064	31.45	253.7
60°	1.098	33.01	218.3	60°	0.9891	28.25	265.7
80°	1.049	29.72	222.6	99°	0.9679	24.13	261.1

$P_{calc.}$ for ring = 207.7 and for open = 237.6. $P_{calc.}$ for ring = 246.7 and for open = 276.6.

TABLE II.

*Diazo-acetic n-propyl ester.**Diazo-acetic n-amyl ester.*P_{calc.} for ring = 285.7 and for open = 315.6. P_{calc.} for ring = 363.7 and for open = 393.6.

Temp.	Density.	Surface tension.	P _{obs.}	Temp.	Density.	Surface tension	P _{obs.}
-5°	0.9954	30.15	301.3	-5°	0.9215	27.85	387.6
0°	0.9896	30.32	303.5	0°	0.9164	27.26	389.0
20°	0.9668	28.90	306.3	20°	0.8817	25.01	394.3
28°	0.9616	28.32	307.0	28°	0.8778	24.40	395.0
60°	0.9260	25.07	309.3	60°	0.8497	21.36	394.7
90°	0.8921	22.34	312.0	98°	0.8177	20.07	403.8

It will be evident from the above tables, that the parachor of the diazo-acetic esters vary with temperature, the value increasing as the temperature is raised. The values above 90° are not very accurate as the compounds are found to decompose to a certain extent on prolonged heating. From the variation of the parachor with temperature it may be definitely said that these compounds are equilibrium mixtures of the two forms. In low temperatures, the tendency is towards the formation of the ring forms while high temperature favours the open-chain structures. At the ordinary temperatures, the value is generally between the values for the two forms. In this connection it should be noted that the increase in the molecular weight of the alcohol radicle of the esters favours the open-chain formation.

After the completion of the present work, it was noticed that Lindermann, Wolter and Groger (*Ber.*, 1930, **66**, 702) determined the parachor of some of the aliphatic diazo-compounds. They observed the parachor at a single temperature and as their values in the majority of cases were found to lie between the values for the two forms, they concluded that these compounds are probably equilibrium mixtures of the two forms. The work carried out by the present author, extending over a wide range of temperature, has definitely settled this point.

In conclusion the author begs to express his thanks to Prof. P. R. Rây of the University College of Science and to Prof. A. Maitra of the Presidency College for their kind interest in the work.